

e-ISSN: 3048-9725

Volume 03 Issue 01
Jan-June 2026

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Submission Date: Nov 12,
2025

Copyright Date : Nov
14,2025

Reason and Remedy of Wild Bio life of rare animals visible in the world

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ABSTRACT

Even though the desi, hybrid, and crossbreed technologies are made, there are also rare cases of visible presence of animals. You cannot see these animals in large numbers; only a few countable animals are seen. But the reality and main cause and effect are different in all nations worldwide. While a person is speaking some words then it may be gone towards Zenith side uurdhva or adho as nadir side and almost in all times around the world as you are all hearing. Sometimes a person goes downward as the lower sky, or sometimes a person's word goes into the lower sky; this impact will result in many bad actions. Finally, the death of animals will happen. This is one of the unwanted bad effects of technology you can feel and call. In earlier times, a very old couple can't say her husband's name at all regions, at all times, and at all places, usually in the past, in the lower sky, or on the Nadir side. If she has told her husband's name in zenith side uurdhva or upper sky level then her husband will be positive energy gaining, as promotions, money gaining, energy gaining in all aspects of her life as being couple. In this paper, why few animals are not visible: they went where, and usually now they are present in lower sky levels in few dimensions. After sense-level death, they went to their places, and now they are a healthy breed as desi animals. Again, the ecosystem will be balanced through technology. There is the main cause by sound wave effect in past as longitudinal waves as in case of sensors will introducing to death of animals.

Keywords: *Wildlife, animals, desi, hybrid, sound waves, zenith upper sky, nadir lower sky*

INTRODUCTION

In the universe, all types of animals are present, but in the case of the planet Earth, only a few animals are to be seen. The main reason is the effect of humans' sound waves, which results in the rare case availability of animals. Like a few years ago, donkeys were in rare countable numbers, and tigers also, and other animals also. There are many ways to regain the counts of animals in the entire world and save the ecosystem in around the world. There will be some politics introducing as because they are made a person availability in lower sky then they will be in conversations then sensor death sensors usually go towards animals and finally death of animals is happening. So, this is the political chain of killing of animal species. In the entire world there are no such laws and orders that control political hitting of a person; this is totally a sense level, as someone is thinking, someone is planning, someone is scheduling, someone is saying, and someone is doing with his technologies or through his bare hands. This is the political chain system to kill the animals. This is the preplan because animal wealth is uncountable in nature; all need to control and save the ecosystem through animals.[1-27]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Don't converse about any matter in any political world language in the form of saying words in lower Nadir side levels. Say unusual words in the lower sky; here sensors play a vital role. So many types of sensors were made for negative energy species, which are going towards unhealthy environments. Sound wave effects in all the sky are different in the entire world and universe. The behaviour of sound waves is entirely specific towards levels of sky in and around the world and universe.

CONCLUSION

1. You cannot see these animals in large numbers; only a few countable animals are seen. But the reality and main cause and effect are different in all nations worldwide.
2. While a person is speaking some words then it may be gone towards Zenith side uurdhva or adho as nadir side and almost in all times around the world as you are all hearing
3. the death of animals will happen. This is one of the unwanted bad effects of technology you can feel and call.
4. In earlier times, a very old couple can't say her husband's name at all regions, always, and at all places, usually in the past, in the lower sky, or on the Nadir side.
5. If she has told her husband's name in zenith side uurdhva or upper sky level then her husband will be positive energy gaining, as promotions, money gaining, energy gaining in all aspects of her life as being couple. In this paper, why few animals are not visible: they went where, and usually now they are present in lower sky levels in few dimensions
6. Don't converse about any matter in any political world language in the form of saying words in lower Nadir side levels.
7. Say unusual words in the lower sky; here sensors play a vital role. So many types of sensors were made for negative energy species, which are going towards unhealthy environments.
8. Sound wave effects in all the sky are different in the entire world and universe.
9. There will be some politics introducing as because they are made a person availability in lower sky then they will be in conversations then sensor death sensors usually go towards animals and finally death of animals is happening.

So, this is the political chain of killing of animal species.

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